

Quantifying the transport properties of lipid mesophases by theoretical modelling of diffusion experiments

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Lytotropic Liquid Crystals (LLCs) are a class of lipid-based membranes with a strong potential for drug-delivery employment. The characterization and control of their transport properties is a central issue in this regard, and has recently prompted a notable volume of research on the topic. A promising experimental approach is provided by the so-called diffusion setup, where the drug molecules diffuse from a feeding chamber filled with water to a receiving one passing through a LLC. In the present work we provide a theoretical framework for the proper description of this setup, and validate it by means of targeted experiments. Due to the inhomogeneity of the system, a rich palette of different diffusion dynamics emerges from the interplay of the different time- and lengthscales thereby present. Our work paves the way to the employment of diffusion experiments to quantitatively characterize the transport properties of LLCs, and provides the basic tools to device diffusion setups with controlled kinetic properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lytotropic Liquid Crystals (LLCs) or lipid mesophases are molecular aggregates resulting from the self-organization of lipids into periodical structures^{1,2}. Their geometrical arrangement creates nanoscopic channels filled by water, and the emerging structure shows a periodicity along one, two or three spatial directions³. Lipid mesophases are very versatile objects, whose employment encompasses applications as diverse as membrane proteins crystallization⁴, materials design⁵, ion pumps⁶ and controlled drug delivery⁷.

Particularly, the high biocompatibility of LLCs⁸ and the heterogeneity and controllability of their structural features¹ render the mesophases potentially unique drug-delivery tools^{7,9,10}. As a consequence, an intense amount of research has been recently focusing on characterizing their transport properties^{3,9-18}. To this aim, a traditional approach is to perform a *release experiment*, which consists in preparing a lipid mesophase loaded with a model drug and putting it in excess-water conditions, *i.e.* using more water than what can be accommodated in the mesophase channels^{3,9,10,12,15-18}. This approach is possible in all those cases in which the specific mesophase of interest is at thermodynamic equilibrium with excess water, notable examples being the columnar hexagonal, and the bicontinuous cubic phases of double diamond and primitive symmetry⁸. In this way, a biphasic system is obtained: the mesophase with its water channels and the

pure water in excess. Due to the concentration gradient between the two phases, as time passes the drug diffuses out of the mesophase. The excess water is periodically substituted in order to mimic perfect-sink conditions, and by measuring the amount of diffused molecules into the removed liquid one can monitor the dynamics of drug release. The system can be macroscopically considered as a homogeneous medium. Indeed, the typical size of a mesophase employed in experiments (order of mm, see *e.g.*¹¹) is much larger than its periodicity or the size of grain boundaries (order of nm and μm respectively^{11,19}), the latter being defined as single-crystal domains within the cubic phase. As a result, from the macroscopical perspective the drug diffuses in the mesophase with an effective diffusion coefficient D_m , whose value is expected to be lower than the diffusion coefficient D_c characterizing the transport in pure water.

More recently^{6,9,11-13}, a second experimental setup has been introduced: in a *diffusion experiment* an initially drug-free mesophase is put in excess-water conditions with two chambers, which can exchange matter only through the LLC. The *feeding chamber* contains a solution of water and drug, while the *receiving chamber* is filled only with pure water. In this way, the drug can pass from the feeding chamber to the receiving one only diffusing through the mesophase. As in the release experiment, the excess water in the receiving chamber is periodically substituted in order to mimic perfect-sink conditions, and the total amount of diffused drug is monitored in time. This setup presents a few advantages compared to the release setup, for example, offering the possibility of introducing a bias potential between the feeding and receiving chamber to study diffusion of ions and charged species⁶.

From the theoretical point of view, the more tradi-

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Exact Solution

Parameters		Transcendental Equation	$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c}$
$\alpha \equiv \frac{L_c^2}{L_m^2} \frac{D_m}{D_c}$	$\beta \equiv k \frac{L_c}{L_m}$	$\frac{\beta}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \tan \lambda_n = \cot(\sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_n)$	$1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \cos \lambda_n e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}}}{\lambda_n^2 [\beta + \beta^2 \sin^2 \lambda_n + \alpha \cos^2 \lambda_n]}$

Approximate Long-Time Solutions

Regime	Conditions	1st order approximation	2nd order approximation
Point Source	$\alpha \ll 1, \beta \ll 1, \frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \geq 20\%$	$1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \exp\left[-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}\right]$	$1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \exp\left[-\frac{\pi^2}{4(1+\beta)^2} \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}\right]$
Chamber Release	$\alpha \gg 1, \alpha \gg \beta, \frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \geq 30\%$	$1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \exp\left[-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_c t}{L_c^2}\right]$	$1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \left(1 + \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right) \exp\left[-\frac{\pi^2}{4\left(1 + \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right)^2} \frac{D_c t}{L_c^2}\right]$
Steady State	$\beta \gg 1, \beta \gg \alpha, \frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \geq 1\%$	$1 - \exp\left(-\frac{D_m t}{k L_c L_m}\right)$	$1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{6\beta}\right) \exp\left[-\left(1 - \frac{1}{6\beta} - \frac{\alpha}{6\beta}\right) \frac{D_m t}{k L_c L_m}\right]$

TABLE I. Exact solution and long-time approximations for the diffusion setup. The parameters defining the system are: the size of the feeding chamber L_c ; the size of the mesophase L_m ; the diffusion coefficient of the drug molecule in water D_c ; the effective diffusion coefficient in the mesophase D_m ; and the partition coefficient k . Any long-time approximation can be written as $1 - c \exp(-st)$, and the corresponding lag time can be computed as $t_{lag} = \ln(c)/s$.

tional approach provided by the release setup has been already analyzed and discussed in the literature^{20–23}. In short, the release experiment is modelled by considering the diffusion equation, where the sink-mimicking protocol is implemented by means of an absorbing boundary condition. Conversely, the diffusion experiment has not yet been the focus of a thorough theoretical investigation, thus hindering the possibility to extract quantitative information from the experimental data. In this work, we fill this gap by solving the diffusion equation relevant to this setup. Apart from finding an analytical solution to the problem, we also provide some useful approximations, which help getting a better grasp of the system. We then validate our theoretical findings by comparing them to experimental data, both novel and already present in the literature. Finally, we discuss efficient ways to use our results for practical purposes and analyze their limits.

II. THEORETICAL RESULTS

The present section is devoted to the theoretical treatment of the diffusion experiment. Though being similar to the release case in spirit, as we show below the diffusion setup is somewhat more complicated to model, due to the presence of the interface separating the feeding

chamber and the mesophase. This issue requires a more refined theoretical toolset, provided by the formalism of the quasi-orthogonal functions²⁴, which has already been successfully employed in different contexts^{25,26}. After some general remarks, we proceed in sec.IIA to the derivation of an analytical solution, while sec.IIB focuses on some useful long-time approximations that can be found when the parameters of the system meet specific conditions. All the results found are summarized in table I.

In the simplest case, a diffusion experimental setup consists of a cylindrical tube where the mesophase is placed between the feeding and the receiving chambers⁹. Due to the symmetry of the setup, the macroscopically-relevant diffusion direction \hat{x} is the one parallel to the axis of the cylinder, thus the problem can be treated in one dimension. Moreover, as in the traditional treatment of the release experiment^{21,27}, the sink-mimicking protocol is taken into account by imposing an absorbing boundary condition at the interface separating the mesophase and the receiving chamber. Therefore, as we show schematically in fig.1, the system can be represented as a feeding chamber of size L_c and where the drug has a diffusion coefficient equal to D_c , and a mesophase of size L_m characterized by a diffusion coefficient equal to D_m . Another crucial quantity is the *partition coefficient*^{3,28–30} k , defined as the equilibrium ratio between the drug con-

FIG. 1. Schematic representation of our model for the diffusion setup.

centration in the mesophase and in pure water when the latter are put in contact with each other. In other words, $k = \exp(-\Delta F/k_B T)$, where ΔF is the change in the free energy of a drug molecule as it passes from the mesophase to pure water, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T the temperature. A value $k > 1$ indicates that water is a more favourable environment for the drug with respect to the mesophase, due *e.g.* to the confinement introduced by excluded-volume interactions between the lipid bilayer and the diffusing molecule or to the presence of repulsive electrostatic interactions between them. Conversely, for $k < 1$ the mesophase is preferred, which could be the case in the presence of hydrophobic or attractive electrostatic interactions.

To summarize, there are five parameters relevant to our description of the system: the sizes L_c and L_m of the two phases, the corresponding diffusion coefficients D_c and D_m , and the partition coefficient k .

A. Exact solution

If $k \neq 1$, the concentration profile at the interface between the feeding chamber and the mesophase is expected to change abruptly. The most efficient way to approach the modelling of the diffusion setup is therefore to split the problem into two separate ones relative to the chamber and the LLC. To this aim, let us consider a coordinate system x where the origin is placed at the interface (fig.1). Denoting as $c_c(x,t)$ and $c_m(x,t)$ the concentration profiles in the chamber and the mesophase respectively, we thus need to solve the diffusion equations

$$\frac{\partial c_c}{\partial t} = -D_c \frac{\partial^2 c_c}{\partial x^2} \quad x \in [-L_c, 0] \quad (1)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial c_m}{\partial t} = -D_m \frac{\partial^2 c_m}{\partial x^2} \quad x \in [0, L_m]. \quad (2)$$

Assuming that at the beginning of the experiment the drug molecules are homogeneously distributed in the feeding chamber, the initial conditions are written as (red

concentration profile in fig.1)

$$c_c(x, 0) = c_0 \quad c_m(x, 0) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Finally, the boundary conditions of the two diffusion problems are determined by assuming the presence of a reflecting wall at the end of the feeding chamber, a sink at the end of the mesophase, and two interface conditions. The latter consist in imposing the continuity of the flux, which is a direct consequence of mass conservation, and assuming that a local equilibrium is attained instantaneously between the chamber and the mesophase (blue profile in fig.1). We thus have

$$\frac{\partial c_c}{\partial x}(-L_c, t) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$c_m(L_m, t) = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$D_c \frac{\partial c_c}{\partial x}(0, t) = D_m \frac{\partial c_m}{\partial x}(0, t), \quad (6)$$

$$c_c(0, t) = k c_m(0, t). \quad (7)$$

As we show in Appendix A, this combination of diffusion equations can be solved by separating the variables and taking into account the discontinuity by means of quasi-orthogonal functions²⁴. Integrating the concentration profiles $c_c(x,t)$ and $c_m(x,t)$ obtained by solving the previous problem, we can easily compute the total amount of drug $M(t)$ present in the chamber and in the mesophase at time t . Therefore, by mass conservation we can calculate the quantity $Q(t)$ of drug molecules that have diffused in the sink as $Q(t) = c_0 L_c - M(t)$. For the full derivation we refer the reader to Appendix A, while here we report only the final result:

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \cos \lambda_n e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}}{\lambda_n^2 [\beta + \beta^2 \sin^2 \lambda_n + \alpha \cos^2 \lambda_n]}, \quad (8)$$

where the subscript n labels all the positive solutions λ_n of the transcendental equation

$$\frac{\beta}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \tan \lambda_n = \cot(\sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_n) \quad (9)$$

and α, β are combinations of the physical parameters of the system:

$$\alpha \equiv \frac{L_c^2 D_m}{L_m^2 D_c}, \quad (10)$$

$$\beta \equiv k \frac{L_c}{L_m}. \quad (11)$$

Apart from an overall timescale, the parameters describing the system enter equations (8) and (9) only by means of the combinations provided by α and β . As a consequence, the physical behavior of the diffusion setup is entirely determined by the latter.

B. Approximate results for the long-time dynamics

Equations (8) and (9) provide the exact solution to the diffusion setup. Their usage for practical purposes relies on the resolution of a transcendental equation, a task for which one usually needs to resort to numerical approaches. However, there are a few limiting cases where the exact solution reduces to a simpler form. Particularly, we shall focus on the long-time behavior, *i.e.* when in equation (8) only the term corresponding to the smallest λ_n is retained. Apart from giving ready-to-use formulas for fitting purposes, this study is also useful to give a deeper physical insight into the system.

Before dwelling on the analysis of these limiting cases, let us consider again the definition of the two parameters α and β introduced above. In this regard, defining $\tau_c \equiv L_c^2/D_c$ and $\tau_m \equiv L_m^2/D_m$ gives $\alpha = \tau_c/\tau_m$. These two timescales are an estimation of the typical time needed for a drug molecule to travel through the chamber and the mesophase, respectively. Therefore, α can be seen as a measure of the relative time spent by a molecule in the feeding chamber as compared to the LLC. As for the parameter β , we notice that it can be written as $\beta = C_c/C_m$, where $C_c = L_c c_{eq}$ and $C_m = L_m c_{eq}/k$, and c_{eq} is a constant introduced here for convenience. These two quantities give the total masses one would find in the two phases in an equilibrium experiment, *i.e.* if the sink was replaced by a reflective wall, with equilibrium concentration equal to c_{eq} . β can thus be seen as a measure of the relative capacity of the two phases, that is, the relative amount of matter the chamber can host as compared to the mesophase. Tuning these parameters, three regimes can be identified, as we report schematically in fig.2.

Point-source regime. If $\alpha \ll 1$ and $\beta \ll 1$, both the size of the feeding chamber and the diffusion process in it can be neglected with respect to the ones in the mesophase, which thus is expected to play a leading role in determining the dynamics of the system. As we show in Appendix B, within this approximation we can solve for λ_n in equation (9), finding for the smallest value λ_1 :

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{\pi}{2(\beta + 1)}. \quad (12)$$

Substituting in equation (8) and taking the limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$, one finds (see Appendix B)

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} e^{-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}}. \quad (13)$$

As expected, only the parameters involving the mesophase are present in the formula. It is worth noting that the previous result corresponds to the long-time behavior of a single-phase diffusion problem $\partial c/\partial t = D_m \partial^2 c/\partial x^2$ with initial condition $c(x, 0) = c_0 L_c \delta(x + L_c)$. This is in line with our physical interpretation: the only role played by the chamber is to determine a point-like initial condition located at the reflecting wall (see

FIG. 2. Top panel: ranges of validity of the three limiting regimes. Central to bottom panels: schematic illustration of the main physical mechanisms at work in each limiting regime.

fig.2). A more precise solution taking into account the leading dependence on the parameters is also reported in table I.

Chamber-release regime. When either α or β are much larger than one, the physics of the diffusion setup is driven by the chamber. Nevertheless, qualitatively-different behaviors are predicted when one quantity is tuned with respect to the other. If $\alpha \gg \beta$ and $\alpha \gg 1$ it can be shown that solving equation (9) gives (see Appendix B)

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{\alpha} \left(1 + \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right)}. \quad (14)$$

Substituting in equation (8) and considering the leading term gives (see Appendix B)

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} e^{-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_c t}{L_c^2}}. \quad (15)$$

From a physical point of view, this situation is exactly the opposite of the point-source regime: since α is the largest parameter, before being absorbed every drug molecule spends virtually the whole time within the chamber (see fig.2). In other words, we can neglect the very existence of the mesophase and the problem reduces to a simple one-sided release from the feeding chamber. This picture is confirmed by a closer look at (15), where only the parameters relative to the chamber are present. Moreover, this formula also formally corresponds to the long-time behavior of a one-sided release²⁷. For completeness, in table I we also report a formula providing the leading correction to equation (15).

Steady-state regime. The third and last regime is found when $\beta \gg \alpha$ and $\beta \gg 1$. In this case solving equation (9) gives (see Appendix B)

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta}} \quad (16)$$

which, once substituted in equation (8), results into (see Appendix B)

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - e^{-\frac{D_m t}{k L_c L_m}}. \quad (17)$$

Conversely to the previous cases, in this regime both the phases are relevant in determining the behavior of the system, though the diffusion coefficient within the chamber D_c does not enter the leading term. Quite interestingly, this result can be obtained at the leading order by assuming an adiabatically-slow absorption process. The physical idea is simple: because of the condition $\beta \gg \alpha$, the difference in capacity between the chamber and the mesophase is the main player in this regime. As a consequence, the chamber instantaneously acts as an infinite source of a given concentration, though at long times the amount of matter in it decreases to the detriment of its function as a reservoir. More precisely, let us assume that at every instant t the mesophase reaches the steady state compatible with a source of constant concentration $c(t)/k$ on one side and a perfect sink on the other side. This steady state corresponds to a linear concentration profile²⁷ (fig.2):

$$c_m(x, t) = \frac{c(t)}{k} \left(1 - \frac{x}{L_m} \right). \quad (18)$$

Analogously, the chamber is at equilibrium with constant concentration $c_c(x, t) = c(t)$. Nevertheless, due to the outflux at the sink the value of $c(t)$ decreases with time (fig.2). The amount of matter flowing out of the system per unit time $\dot{Q}(t)$ is easily found by computing the flux $-D_m \partial c_m / \partial x$ at $x = L_m$ ²⁷, giving

$$\dot{Q}(t) = D_m c(t) / (k L_m). \quad (19)$$

By conservation of mass, we also have

$$Q(t) = c_0 L_c - c(t) \left(L_c + \frac{L_m}{2k} \right) \simeq c_0 L_c - c(t) L_c, \quad (20)$$

where we neglected the contribution coming from the mesophase due to the condition $\beta \gg 1$. Differentiating the last formula with respect to time and comparing the result with equation (19), we find

$$\dot{c}(t) = -\frac{D_m}{k L_m L_c} c(t), \quad (21)$$

whose resolution gives

$$c(t) = c_0 e^{-\frac{D_m t}{k L_m L_c}}. \quad (22)$$

Substituting this formula into equation (20) results into equation (17). In table I we also report for completeness the leading correction to equation (17).

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The theoretical results obtained in section II were validated by comparison with some simple experiments. Specifically, we considered the data from Negrini *et al.*¹¹ relative to the diffusion of glucose molecules in a LLC with $Pn3m$ topology. In the experimental setup used in that work, the size of the feeding chamber and the mesophase were respectively $L_c = 30$ mm and $L_m = 5$ mm. Moreover, the diffusion coefficient of glucose in pure water at 20 °C has been determined experimentally³¹ to be equal to $0.67 \cdot 10^{-5}$ cm²/s = 2.41 mm²/h. From this value, we can easily estimate the diffusion coefficient in the present context (37 °C) by means of the Stokes-Einstein equation³² $D_c = k_B T / (6\pi\eta r)$, where η is the viscosity of water and r the hydrodynamic radius of glucose. Assuming r to be independent of temperature and considering the empirical formula³³ $\log \eta = -4.5318 - 220.57 / (149.39 - T)$, where T is expressed in Kelvin, we obtain for the diffusion coefficient at 37 °C $D_c \simeq 3.7$ mm²/h.

In order to apply the exact solution provided by equations (8) and (9), the values of D_m and k need to be determined. To this aim, we performed a release and an equilibrium experiment (defined below) on a mesophase with the same microscopic features as the one considered by Negrini *et al.*¹¹ (see Appendix C for experimental details).

As for the release experiment, we considered a mesophase with size $h = 6$ mm in contact with two receiving chambers⁹. As mentioned in the introduction, this setup can be modelled by solving the diffusion equation with absorbing boundary conditions, leading to the well-known result according to which the release profile scales as \sqrt{t} in the short-time regime. To fit our data, we opted for the complete solution based on an expansion

FIG. 3. Top panel: release data from the experiment performed in the present work and corresponding fit. Bottom panel: comparison between the diffusion data through a $Pn3m$ mesophase by Negrini and coworkers¹¹ and theoretical predictions based on our release and equilibrium experiments.

in negative exponentials, which enables fitting also the saturation regime of the release curve. The final formula for the normalized total amount of released drug reads²¹

$$Q_{rel} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} e^{-(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 \frac{D_m t}{h^2}} \quad (23)$$

By considering the terms up to $n = 10$ in the previous formula, we fitted the release data by tuning the diffusion coefficient. The experimental data and the best fit are reported in the top panel of fig.3, and the optimizing parameter is equal to $D_m = (0.79 \pm 0.02) \text{ mm}^2/\text{h}$.

In order to determine the value of k , we further performed an equilibrium experiment, where a glucose-free mesophase of volume $V_m = 194 \mu\text{L}$ was put in contact with a glucose solution with volume $V_c = 200 \mu\text{L}$ and initial concentration $c_i = 21.6 \text{ mM}$. After seven days of equilibration the amount of glucose in the solution

was measured again, yielding $c_f = 17.5 \text{ mM}$. Assuming that the system has achieved equilibrium, from conservation of mass it follows that $c_i V_c = c_f V_c + c_f V_m/k$, from which the partition coefficient can be easily derived as $k = c_f V_m / (c_i - c_f) V_c \simeq 4.14$. A value of k greater than one could have easily been expected. Indeed, from a microscopic perspective the glucose hardly interacts with the lipid bilayer in the mesophase, thus at a first approximation one can assume that the latter acts as a hard obstacle, which confines the glucose molecules in the water channels. Based on this assumption and neglecting the size of glucose, the free-energy change ΔF experienced by a molecule when passing from the mesophase to pure water is mainly due to the smaller available space. Specifically, if V_m is the total volume of the mesophase and V_w the volume thereby occupied by the water channels, one has simply $\Delta F = -k_B T \log(V_m/V_w) < 0$. Consequently, the partition coefficient is equal to $k = \exp(-\Delta F/k_B T) = V_m/V_w = 1/\phi$, where ϕ is the volume fraction of water in the mesophase. In the present experimental conditions, $\phi \simeq 0.37$ and as a result $k \simeq 2.7$, which is in fair agreement with the experimental value. The underestimation of the theoretical k is most likely due to the fact that the finite size of the glucose was neglected in the computation.

Plugging the values of the various parameters into equations (8) and (9) leads to our prediction for the experiments performed by Negrini *et al.*¹¹. As we show in the bottom panel of fig.3, the experimental values for the diffused amount of glucose (black stars) and our theoretical prediction (red continuous curve) agree very well with each other, thus validating our theory against real data. As a side note, we remark that in the present work the quantification of glucose was obtained by means of an enzymatic assay³ (see Appendix C), while Negrini *et al.* based their measurements on the Optical Rotation Dispersion technique¹¹. In this regard, the striking quantitative agreement between the diffusion data and our theory is also indicative of the high reliability of these detection techniques as well as the nice reproducibility of the experiments.

Substitution of the parameters values into equations (10) and (11) gives $\alpha \simeq 7.7$ and $\beta \simeq 25.6$. According to our analysis in section IIB, the behavior of the system should thus be fairly described by the steady-state approximations. In fig.3 we report for comparison also the curves obtained by considering the first- (green dashed curve) and second-order approximations (blue dot-dashed curve) reported in table I. The agreement with the experimental data is still quite good, though both approximations slightly overestimate the actual diffusion rate of the drug molecules.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the physical point of view, the diffusion setup shows a rich set of qualitatively-different behaviors, which are ultimately due to the presence of different time- and length-scales. As we have shown in section II, there are three limiting regimes corresponding to different relative magnitudes of these scales. An important qualitative difference among the various regimes is found in the comparison between the long-time behavior and the initial uptake of diffusion. Indeed, the approximations reported in table I intersect the time axis in correspondence of the *lag time* t_{lag} , which is determined by the prefactor of the exponential. Specifically, if one writes in general any long-time approximation as $1 - c \exp(-st)$, the intercept is found at $t_{lag} = \ln(c)/s$. A comparison with the first-order approximations shows immediately that t_{lag} is positive for the point-source regime, negative for the chamber-release region and practically zero for the steady-state case. The latter is true only at leading order, but it means that in practice the lag time for the steady-state regime can be neglected in comparison to the diffusion timescale. From the physical point of view, one can look at t_{lag} as the timescale needed to fill the mesophase in the point-source and steady-state regimes. However, this interpretation is not rigorous and cannot be applied to the chamber-release case, where the shift of the long-time approximation towards negative times ($t_{lag} < 0$) is just a mathematical consequence of the qualitatively-different short-time behavior between a single exponential and the fast initial uptake of the actual diffusion $Q \sim \sqrt{t}$. This feature implies that, for the chamber-release regime, the long-time approximate solutions given in table I are not applicable at short times, since they would result into an unphysical $\sim 20\%$ of instantaneously-diffused drug at $t = 0$. This is not a major threat, however, since this is the least interesting case from an experimental perspective, as we discuss below.

Another important lesson that can be learnt from the first-order approximations reported in table I is that within each regime only partial information about the transport properties of the mesophase can be gathered. Specifically, well within the point-source region of the parameters space only the value of D_m can be extracted from the fit. Analogously, in the steady-state regime only the ratio D_m/k can be accessed, while for the chamber-release case the dynamics is mainly driven by D_c . In other words, if both the parameters D_m and k are unknown it is not possible in any regime to determine D_m and k from a fit. This could be expected, since in the bulk of each region of the parameters space there is a specific physical mechanism driving the dynamics of the system.

For experimental purposes, a customary approach is to look at the initial uptake of the diffusion curve. When the system is found well within the chamber-release regime, the total amount of diffused molecules shows the typi-

cal one-sided release behavior $Q(t) \simeq 2\sqrt{D_c t / (\pi L_c^2)}$ for percentages up to roughly 60%²¹. Unfortunately, this upper bound goes drastically down as one moves towards the transition lines. The situation improves when one considers the long-time approximations reported in table I, which attain an absolute error of less than 0.01 when considering diffused percentages larger than 30% within a wider region of the parameters space. However, we stress that in this regime the relevant transport property is the diffusion coefficient of the drug in pure water, which is of little interest for the typical purposes of a diffusion experiment. As for the point-source regime, a customary calculation based on the Laplace transforms²⁷ shows that for $t \rightarrow 0$ one has $Q(t)/c_0 L_c \simeq 2\text{erfc}\sqrt{L_m^2/(4D_m t)}$, where erfc is the complementary error function. This behavior is at the origin of the positive lag time described above, but it is of poor utility for fitting purposes. Again, a better approximation is provided by the long-time behavior. Specifically, far enough from the transition lines an absolute error smaller than 0.01 is obtained when considering diffused percentages of at least 20%. This minimum percentage goes down to 1% in the case of the steady-state regime, which is a direct consequence of the corresponding negligible lag time. Therefore, in a typical experiment where the parameters fulfill the requirements of the latter regime, the initial uptake of the diffusion is practically linear with time.

From a practical perspective, one is usually interested in determining the key parameters involving the transport properties of the mesophase, namely the effective diffusion coefficient D_m and the partition coefficient k . In this regard, in the chamber-release regime one can hardly find useful information on D_m and k , and should therefore suitably build the experimental setup in order to avoid this region of the parameters space. Fortunately, this goal can easily be achieved by setting $L_c \leq L_m$. Indeed, in this case $\alpha \leq D_m/D_c < 1$, which ensures that the system will either be in the point-source or the steady-state regimes (fig.2). Moreover, for the particular case of equal-sized feeding chamber and mesophase we also have $\beta = k$. If the drug molecule has weak or no attractive interactions with the lipids (as in the case of glucose in the previous section), being in the mesophase results into a mere drop of its translational entropy. Hence, in this case the pure water is a more favourable environment, *i.e.* $k > 1$ and the diffusion dynamics can be approximately described by the steady-state formulas (table I). Conversely, if the drug molecule has a high affinity for the lipids, *e.g.* because of hydrophobic interactions, the enthalpic term of the free energy can overcome the entropy drop, ultimately resulting into $k < 1$, that is, a point-source dynamics (fig.2). Once the working regime has been identified, the values of the accessible parameters can be found fitting the data with the suitable long-time approximation formula.

A complementary, more general approach relies on considering the first term of the exact solution (8). Fitting the experimental data with the formula $1 - c \exp(-st)$

and comparing to equation (8) truncated at the first term yields

$$c = \frac{2 \cos \lambda_1}{\lambda_1^2 [\beta + \beta^2 \sin^2 \lambda_1 + \alpha \cos^2 \lambda_1]} \quad (24)$$

and

$$s = \lambda_1^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2}. \quad (25)$$

Making use of equations (9), (10) and (11), the previous

formulas can be rearranged in order to provide explicit formulas for λ_1 and k :

$$\lambda_1 = L_m \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_m}}; \quad (26)$$

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \cot \left(L_m \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_m}} \right) \cot \left(L_c \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_c}} \right); \quad (27)$$

$$k = \frac{L_m}{2L_c \sin^2 \lambda_1} \left\{ -1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{L_c}{L_m} \right)^2 \frac{D_m}{D_c} \sin^2 2\lambda_1 + \frac{4 \sin 2\lambda_1 \sin \lambda_1}{c\lambda_1^2}} \right\}. \quad (28)$$

Assuming that the only unknown parameters of the system are k and D_m , making use of equation (26) and equating the right-hand sides of equations (27) and (28) results into an equation where the only unknown is D_m , since s and c are accessible experimentally from the best fit of the diffusion data. The root corresponding to a positive value of k and to $\lambda_1 < \pi/2$ allows thus to extract the relevant parameters from the fitted curve. As an example, we numerically produced some points (represented as black stars in the top panel of fig.4) corresponding to the choice of parameters $L_c = L_m = 10$ mm, $D_c = 3.7$ mm²/h, $D_m = 0.3D_c \simeq 1.1$ mm²/h and $k = 0.9$. With this combination we obtain $\alpha = 0.3$ and $\beta = 0.9$, thus the system is found close to the transition line between the point-source and steady-state regimes. Fitting the points corresponding to at least 30% of diffused molecules by means of the function $1 - c \exp(-st)$ leads to the optimal curve depicted as a red continuous line in the top panel of fig.4. We note that the exponential fit crosses the time axis at a positive value, *i.e.* the lag time t_{lag} is positive, which correctly points towards the conclusion that the system lies in the point-source regime. In the bottom panel we report the corresponding difference of the right-hand sides of equations (27) and (28) as a function of D_m , and denote as a blue star the intersection with the D_m axis. The numerical value of the root $D_m \simeq 1.1$ mm²/h is in perfect agreement with the one used to generate the data. Analogously, plugging this value in either equation (27) or equation (28) gives $k \simeq 0.91$, which again agrees with the original value of the partition coefficient.

As a further example, we applied the same approach to fit the diffusion data of glucose in a mesophase with $Im3m$ topology measured by Negrini *et al.*¹¹. As we show in the top panel of fig.5, the experimental data are nicely fitted by the function $1 - c \exp(-st)$ with $c \simeq 1.02$ and $s \simeq 0.0033$ h⁻¹. In this case, the lag time is quite close to zero, suggesting that the system is found within the steady-state regime. Following the same technique as

above, we obtain $D_m \simeq 0.6$ mm²/h and $k \simeq 0.9$. Substituting these values into equations (10) and (11) together with the known parameters $L_c = 30$ mm, $L_m = 5$ mm and $D_c = 3.7$ mm²/h, we find $\alpha \simeq 6.3$ and $\beta \simeq 5.4$. According to these values, the system is close to the transition line between the chamber-release and steady-state regimes. Nevertheless, these values are to be taken with caution. As we discussed above, for a system in the bulk of the steady-state regime only the ratio D_m/k can be accurately determined, while well within the chamber-release region no information about the properties of the mesophase is available. A numerical check shows that, keeping constant $D_m/k = 0.7$ mm²/h, one can tune the value of the diffusion coefficient in almost the whole range $[0, D_c]$ without strongly affecting the goodness of the fit (bottom panel in fig.5). This may also explain the value obtained from the fit for the partition coefficient. Indeed, as we mentioned above glucose hardly interacts with the lipid bilayer, apart from excluded-volume interactions, thus a value $k > 1$ is expected. Proceeding as we did for the $Pn3m$ topology, starting from a water volume fraction equal to¹¹ $\phi \simeq 0.48$ we estimated that $k \simeq 2.1$. Considering that the fit is sensitive only to the ratio D_m/k , this value of k is compatible with a diffusion coefficient $D_m \simeq 1.5$ mm²/h. Apart from the intrinsic interest of this specific experimental example, this study evidences an important issue regarding the simultaneous determination of both k and D_m from experimental data: after having performed the fit one should always check the position of the system in the parameter space in order to assess the significance of the obtained fitting values.

The analysis performed in this section can be summarized as follows. First of all, it is always a good practice to have an estimation of the partition coefficient k , based on known general properties of both the mesophase and the diffusing molecule, such as the confinement in the LLC introduced by the presence of the bilayer or the possible presence of hydrophobic interac-

FIG. 4. Top panel: numerical data produced for $\alpha = 0.3$ and $\beta = 0.9$, and corresponding long-time fit by means of the equation $1 - c \exp(-st)$. Bottom panel: graphical resolution for the transcendental equation obtained computing the difference between the right-hand sides of equations (27) and (28).

tions between the drug and the lipids. Second, if the experiment has been run for a time long enough for the diffusion data to reach a large percentage ($\geq 60\%$), one can fit the data corresponding to at least the 30% of diffused drug with the long-time approximation, $1 - c \exp(-st)$. The sign of the intercept of the fitting curve with the time axis, $t_{lag} = \ln(c)/s$, enables the characterization of the regime where the system lies: $t_{lag} > 0$, $t_{lag} < 0$ and $t_{lag} = 0$ correspond respectively to the point-source, chamber-release and steady-state regimes. Moreover, in the latter case also the points below the 30% threshold are expected to be well described by the fit. According to the specific regime identified, the available parameters can then be extracted considering the approximations reported in table I. In addition, a complementary analysis can be carried by numerically solving the equation found by comparing the right-hand sides of (27) and (28), which

FIG. 5. Top panel: diffusion data of glucose through an $Im3m$ mesophase by Negrini and coworkers¹¹ and corresponding fit by means of the equation $1 - c \exp(-st)$. Bottom panel: characterization of the significance of the values of D_m and k extracted from the fit by means of the exact solution (8). The contour plot shows the cumulated relative displacement of the exact formula from the experimental data. The white dashed line corresponds to the ratio $D_m/k = 0.7 \text{ mm}^2/\text{h}$ as determined from the best-fitting procedure presented in the main text.

leads to an estimation of both the parameters D_m and k . However, one should always keep in mind that the significance of the values obtained depends on the corresponding position in the parameter space. Therefore, this last approach should only be used as a countercheck of the approximate formulas, or complemented by a systematic analysis comparing the exact solution (8) to the experimental data when D_m and k are tuned within the neighborhood of the identified values (see *e.g.* the bottom panel in fig.5). Naturally, if either D_m or k is known

from other experiments, the numerical approach enables a more precise estimation of the remaining parameter. Finally, if the diffusion data do not reach large percentages (less than 60%), only a system within the steady-state regime can be properly analyzed without implementing the full solution (8). If this is the case, one can either consider one of the approximations from table I (valid from $\sim 1\%$ of diffused molecules) or simply resort to their linear expansion, which in the simplest case reads $Q/c_0L_c \simeq D_m t / (kL_cL_m)$.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work we have addressed the theoretical treatment of the diffusion setup, an experimental approach recently developed in the studies of the transport properties of mesophases. Based on a simplified one-dimensional description, we derived an exact formula for the dependence on the amount of diffused drug molecules as a function of time, which is the typical quantity measured in experiments.

The diffusion dynamics of the drug molecules was shown to be very heterogeneous, according to the relative magnitude of the different parameters describing the system. Particularly, a key role is played by the effective diffusion coefficient of the drug molecule in the mesophase, and by its partition coefficient in the water-mesophase system. By considering the possible limiting cases, we identified three qualitatively-different regimes, whose dynamics are driven by different physical mechanisms.

We benchmarked our findings against real data by considering the diffusion experiments performed by Negrini and coworkers¹¹. Rather than fitting the data with our formula, we performed independent experiments to determine the values of all the parameters. Subsequently, we merely plugged the latter into the exact solution, which shows a perfect agreement with the data by Negrini *et al*, thus unequivocally confirming our theory.

Finally, we showed how our results can be used in practice in order to extract the values of the key quantities D_m and k of the mesophase-water system, and discussed the theoretical limits to their proper characterization.

Through our findings, the diffusion experiment can be employed to quantitatively characterize the transport properties of mesophases. From a more general perspective, our results also provide a solid starting point to build targeted setups, aimed at characterizing or exploiting any of the above-mentioned physical mechanisms involved in the diffusing dynamics of molecules through heterogeneous media.

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APPENDIX A: DERIVATION OF THE EXACT SOLUTION

In order to solve the combined system of differential equations provided by (1)-(7), we follow the classical prescription based on the separation of variables^{27,34}. In this regard, we seek elementary solutions of the form $c_c = X_c(x)T(t)$ and $c_m = X_m(x)T(t)$. Note that the temporal part is assumed to be independent of space, thus the function $T(t)$ needs to be the same for both problems. Substitution of the previous formulas into equations (1) and (2) gives

$$T(t) = e^{-\lambda^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$X_c(x) = a_c \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \lambda \frac{x}{L_m}\right) + b_c \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \lambda \frac{x}{L_m}\right), \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$X_m(x) = a_m \cos\left(\lambda \frac{x}{L_m}\right) + b_m \sin\left(\lambda \frac{x}{L_m}\right), \quad (\text{A3})$$

where the parameters a_c, b_c, a_m, b_m and λ are determined imposing the boundary and initial conditions.

In homogeneous systems this computation is straightforward: the set of elementary solutions compatible with the boundary conditions form an orthogonal basis of the solution space with the usual scalar product $\langle f, g \rangle = \int f \cdot g dx$. Therefore, projecting the initial condition onto this basis gives the general formula for the concentration profile as a linear combination of the elementary solutions. Nevertheless, in the present context the discontinuity at the interface complicates the matter. Indeed, because of it the piecewise functions obtained combining X_c and X_m are not orthogonal with the standard scalar product, and thus cannot be properly used as a basis for the expansion of the solution. A simple and elegant solution is provided by the *quasi-orthogonal functions*²⁴, and consists in considering a slightly-modified scalar product, namely $\langle f, g \rangle = \int_{-L_c}^0 f \cdot g dx + k \int_0^{L_m} f \cdot g dx$. Within this framework, it can be shown that the combinations of the functions X_c and X_m form an orthogonal basis of the solution space in the whole range $[-L_c, L_m]$, with

normalization factor

$$N = \frac{L_m}{2} \left[(a_c^2 + b_c^2) \frac{L_c}{L_m} + (a_m^2 + b_m^2) k \right], \quad (\text{A4})$$

thus enabling a proper application of the initial condition²⁴. Imposing the boundary conditions provided by equations (4)-(7) to the elementary solutions (A2) and (A3) and projecting on the latter the initial condition (3) gives

$$k \sqrt{\frac{D_c}{D_m}} \tan \lambda = \cot \left(\frac{L_c}{L_m} \sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \lambda \right) \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$b_m = -\frac{2c_0 \cos^2 \lambda}{\lambda \left[k + k^2 \frac{L_c}{L_m} \sin^2 \lambda + \frac{L_c}{L_m} \frac{D_m}{D_c} \cos^2 \lambda \right]}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$a_m = -b_m \tan \lambda, \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$a_c = -b_m k \tan \lambda, \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$b_c = b_m \sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}}. \quad (\text{A9})$$

For each λ solving (A5), the other parameters are univocally determined through equations (A6)-(A9). Substituting (A7)-(A9) into equations (A2) and (A3) and rearranging, we find for the elementary solutions

$$X_{c,n} = b_{m,n} \left[-k \tan \lambda_n \cos \left(\sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \lambda_n \frac{x}{L_m} \right) + \sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \sin \left(\sqrt{\frac{D_m}{D_c}} \lambda_n \frac{x}{L_m} \right) \right] \quad (\text{A10})$$

and

$$X_{m,n} = b_{m,n} \left[-\tan \lambda_n \cos \left(\lambda_n \frac{x}{L_m} \right) + \sin \left(\lambda_n \frac{x}{L_m} \right) \right], \quad (\text{A11})$$

where we introduced the subscript n to label the different positive solutions of (A5), ordered increasingly: $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots$. The concentration profile can be written as a linear combination of the elementary solutions:

$$c_c(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_{c,n}(x) e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}, \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$c_m(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_{m,n}(x) e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}, \quad (\text{A13})$$

From the concentration profile, one can easily compute the total amount of drug in the chamber $M_c(t) = \int_{-L_c}^0 c_c(x, t) dx$ and in the mesophase $M_m(t) = \int_0^{L_m} c_m(x, t) dx$ as a function of time, finding:

$$M_c(t) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{b_{m,n} L_m e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}}{\lambda_n}, \quad (\text{A14})$$

$$M_m(t) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{b_{m,n} L_m e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}}{\lambda_n} \left(\frac{1}{\cos \lambda_n} - 1 \right). \quad (\text{A15})$$

Finally, from conservation of mass we can calculate the total amount of diffused drug $Q(t) = c_0 L_c - M_c(t) - M_m(t)$, obtaining

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} = 1 - \frac{L_m}{c_0 L_c} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-b_{m,n}}{\lambda_n \cos \lambda_n} e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}. \quad (\text{A16})$$

Substituting equation (A6) gives the final formula

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} = 1 - \frac{L_m}{L_c} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \cos \lambda_n e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}}{\lambda_n^2 \left[k + k^2 \frac{L_c}{L_m} \sin^2 \lambda_n + \frac{L_c}{L_m} \frac{D_m}{D_c} \cos^2 \lambda_n \right]}. \quad (\text{A17})$$

Defining

$$\alpha \equiv \frac{L_c^2}{L_m^2} \frac{D_m}{D_c}, \quad (\text{A18})$$

and

$$\beta \equiv k \frac{L_c}{L_m}. \quad (\text{A19})$$

The key equations (A5) and (A17) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\beta}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \tan \lambda_n = \cot(\sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_n) \quad (\text{A20})$$

and

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \cos \lambda_n e^{-\lambda_n^2 \frac{D_m}{L_m^2} t}}{\lambda_n^2 [\beta + \beta^2 \sin^2 \lambda_n + \alpha \cos^2 \lambda_n]}. \quad (\text{A21})$$

Thus, apart from a timescale factor, the physical behavior of the system is completely determined by the two parameters α and β .

APPENDIX B: LONG-TIME BEHAVIOR IN LIMITING CASES

In the present section we derive, within the three limiting cases analyzed in section II B, some approximate

solutions to equation (9), which we report here for convenience:

$$\frac{\beta}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \tan \lambda_n = \cot(\sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_n). \quad (9)$$

Specifically, we shall compute the smallest solution λ_1 , which provides the longest timescale of the dynamics of the system. To this aim, we note that the left-hand side of equation (9) grows monotonically from 0 to ∞ as λ is tuned within the interval $[0, \pi/2]$ (fig.6). Analogously, the right-hand side decreases from ∞ to 0 in the range $[0, \pi/2\sqrt{\alpha}]$. As a consequence, the smallest positive solution λ_1 to equation (9), corresponding to the intersection between these two curves, lies in the range $[0, \min\{\pi/2, \pi/2\sqrt{\alpha}\}]$.

Point-source regime. In this case, by definition $\alpha \ll 1$ and $\beta \ll 1$. Within this region, the intersection is expected to be found very close to $\pi/2$ (top panel in fig.6). Indeed, since $\lambda_1 \leq \pi/2$, the argument of the cotangent in the right-hand side of equation (9) is small, thus $\cot(\sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_1) \simeq 1/(\sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_1)$. Substituting into equation (9), the latter is reduced to $\beta \tan \lambda_1 \simeq 1/\lambda_1$, *i.e.* $\tan \lambda_1 \simeq 1/(\beta\lambda_1) \gg 1$. For this condition to hold, λ_1 needs to be very close to $\pi/2$ (top panel in fig.6), thus at leading order $\tan \lambda_1 \simeq 1/(\pi/2 - \lambda_1)$. Substituting these approximations back into equation (9) results into a simple algebraic equation whose solution is

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{\pi}{2(\beta + 1)}. \quad (B1)$$

Let us now consider the long-time behavior of equation (8), that corresponds to λ_1 :

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - \frac{2 \cos \lambda_1 e^{-\lambda_1^2 \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}}}{\lambda_1^2 [\beta + \beta^2 \sin^2 \lambda_1 + \alpha \cos^2 \lambda_1]}. \quad (B2)$$

Remembering that $\beta \ll 1$, at leading order we have $\lambda_1 \simeq \pi/2$, $\cos \lambda_1 \simeq \beta\pi/2$ and $\sin \lambda_1 \simeq 1$. The first-order approximation for the long-time behavior of the point-source regime can be obtained by substitution of the previous formulas into equation (B2) and retaining only the leading term. The final result reads

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} e^{-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_m t}{L_m^2}}. \quad (B3)$$

Chamber-release regime. In this case, we have $\alpha \gg \beta$ and $\alpha \gg 1$, and the solution to the transcendental equation is expected to be in the vicinity of $\pi/2\sqrt{\alpha}$ (central panel in fig.6). Indeed, since $\alpha \gg 1$ one has $0 < \lambda_1 < \pi/(2\sqrt{\alpha}) \ll 1$, thus $\tan \lambda_1 \simeq \lambda_1$. As a consequence, the left-hand side of equation (9) is very small, implying that also the condition $\cot(\sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_1) \ll 1$ needs to be fulfilled, enabling the expansion $\cot(\sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_1) \simeq \pi/2 - \sqrt{\alpha}\lambda_1$. Within these approximations, equation (9) can again be solved, finding

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{\alpha} \left(1 + \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right)}. \quad (B4)$$

FIG. 6. Graphical resolution of equation (9) in the three limiting cases.

In order to determine the long-time behavior, we need to plug the previous result into equation (B2). In this case, at leading order one has $\lambda_1 \simeq \pi/(2\sqrt{\alpha})$, $\cos \lambda_1 \simeq 1$ and $\sin \lambda_1 \simeq \lambda_1 \simeq \pi/(2\sqrt{\alpha})$. Therefore, after substitution into (B2) we easily obtain at leading order

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} e^{-\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{D_c t}{L_c^2}}. \quad (B5)$$

Steady-state regime. In this region of the parameters

space the conditions $\beta \gg \alpha$ and $\beta \gg 1$ imply that the arguments of both the trigonometric functions in equation (9) are very small (bottom panel in fig.6). Indeed, rearranging equation (9) we can write

$$\tan \lambda_1 \tan \sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_1 = \sqrt{\alpha}/\beta \ll 1. \quad (\text{B6})$$

This implies that at least one of the tangents is very small. If $\alpha \ll 1$, one has $\tan(\sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_1) \simeq \sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_1$ and equation (B6) can be recast as $\lambda_1 \tan \lambda_1 = 1/\beta$. Since $\beta \gg 1$, the previous result implies that $\lambda_1 \ll 1$, which further simplifies (B6) into $\lambda_1^2 \simeq 1/\beta$, finally giving

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta}}. \quad (\text{B7})$$

If the condition $\alpha \ll 1$ does not hold, equation (B6) implies $\lambda_1 \ll 1$, *i.e.* $\tan \lambda_1 \simeq \lambda_1$. Defining $p \equiv \sqrt{\alpha} \lambda_1$, we can rewrite (B6) as $p \tan p = \alpha/\beta$. Since $\beta \gg \alpha$, the previous result implies that $p \ll 1$, and equation (B6) becomes $p^2 \simeq \alpha/\beta$, finally yielding the same result for λ_1 as in the case $\alpha \ll 1$.

As for the long-time behavior, in this case at leading order $\sin \lambda_1 \simeq \lambda_1 \simeq 1/\sqrt{\beta}$ and $\cos \lambda_1 \simeq 1$. Substituting these approximations into equation (B2) finally yields at the leading order

$$\frac{Q(t)}{c_0 L_c} \simeq 1 - e^{-\frac{D_m t}{\kappa L_c L_m}}. \quad (\text{B8})$$

APPENDIX C: EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dimodan U/J, from Danisco (Denmark), was used as received. This commercial-grade form of monolinolein (MLO) contains more than 98 wt% monoglyceride. The same batch of Dimodan was used throughout the whole work. Glucose oxidase (GO) from *Aspergillus niger*, horseradish peroxidase (HRP), 2,2-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) (ABTS) and buffer solutions were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. d-(+)-Glucose was obtained from Fluka. MilliQ water was used for all sample and solution preparations.

Sample preparation. The double diamond cubic phase ($Pn\bar{3}m$) contained 64 wt% MLO and 36 wt% sodium acetate buffer pH 4.62 (with the addition of 50 Mm Glucose in the case of the release experiments). The liquid crystalline mesophases were prepared by mixing weighed quantities of MLO and buffer inside sealed Pyrex glass tubes followed by vortexing and centrifugation until a homogenous mixture was obtained. The prepared mesophase was then allowed to equilibrate at 37 °C in an incubator; the obtained cubic phase was then characterized by small-angle X-ray diffraction (top panel in fig.7). Release experiments were performed in triplicate sets using the home-built setup described by Negrini *et al.*⁹. For each triplicate, three independent mesophases

were prepared. Briefly, 300 mg of bulk mesophase containing Glucose were placed into the middle of the sample holder, a poly(methyl methacrylate) tube closed at both sides by two Teflon lids; the experiment was started filling the tube with 1 mL of sodium acetate buffer pH 4.62 at each side of the cubic phase. The two solutions were periodically removed to measure the amount of Glucose released with time. At the end of the release experiments, the mesophase was removed and characterized by small-angle X-ray diffraction. For the equilibrium studies, 200 μL of 21.6 mM Glucose in sodium acetate buffer pH 4.62 were added on top of 200 mg of pre-equilibrated cubic phase inside a Pyrex tube. Experiments were performed in triplicate sets, using three independent mesophases. After 7 days the solution was collected to measure the amount of Glucose diffused from the excess solution to the cubic phase. At the end of the equilibrium experiments the mesophase was again characterized by small-angle X-ray diffraction. Glucose was quantified following the enzymatic assay reported by Martiel *et al.*³, involving oxidation of glucose by GO and reduction of the product H_2O_2 by HRP, which oxidized the colored substrate ABTS. The conversion rate of ABTS is directly proportional to the available glucose concentration. The initial slope was used in the determination of the glucose concentration (calibration curve in the bottom panel of fig.7).

Small-Angle X-Ray Scattering Measurements. SAXS measurements were used to identify the symmetry of the mesophases at the different conditions. Experiments were performed on a Bruker AXS Micro, with a microfocussed X-Ray source, operating at voltage and filament current of 50 kV and 1000 μA , respectively. The Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda_{\text{Cu } K\alpha} = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) was collimated by a 2D Kratky-collimator and the data were collected by a 2D Pilatus 100K detector. The scattering vector $q = (4\pi/\lambda) \sin \theta$, with 2θ being the scattering angle, was calibrated using silver behenate. Data were collected and azimuthally averaged using the SaxsGui software to yield one-dimensional intensity versus scattering vector q , with a q range from 0.004 to 0.5 \AA^{-1} . For all measurements the samples were placed inside a stainless steel cell between two thin replaceable mica sheets and sealed by an O-ring, with a sample volume of 10 μL and a thickness of approximately 1 mm. Measurements were performed at 37 °C, and samples were equilibrated for 15 min prior to measurements, while scattered intensity was collected over 20 min.

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FIG. 7. Top panel: 1D SAXS spectra of scattered intensities versus scattering vector q for the cubic phase before and after release/equilibrium experiments (Log-Lin scale). The $Pn3m$ symmetry and the structural parameters are maintained throughout the entire diffusion process. Bottom panel: calibration curve of glucose from the initial slope of the absorbance at 415 nm in sodium acetate buffer pH 4.62.

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